

Curriculum for Data Professionals in Research Performing Organisations in the Netherlands

Research Data Netherlands

About this document

This document was established by a dedicated task group within Research Data Netherlands (RDNL), in consultation with RDNL members, a selection of training providers, and individual data stewards. This is version 1.0, established as a first deliverable in December 2025 of an Open Science NL-funded project (2025-2028). The document will be updated at regular intervals after broader evaluation by key stakeholders. A final version will be published before the end of the RDNL project in 2028.

Acknowledgements

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1. Introduction

This document is the first deliverable of the Research Data Netherlands (RDNL) project to build a National training and community platform for research data professionals.¹ This project is funded by Open Science NL as part of its work programme 2024-2025 in the area ‘Capacity building for Open Science’² and aims to provide national-level training and community support for aspiring data professionals. The project started in January 2025 and will run for four years.

Over the past twelve years, RDNL has trained several hundred data professionals within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) through its trainings ‘Essentials 4 Data Support’ and ‘GDPR 4 Data Support’. Through the project, we envision to expand and sustain our training activities. Moreover, RDNL will intensify the collaboration with training providers, data stewards and their communities, and RPOs to ensure that this curriculum evolves - in time - into a national training programme that is widely supported and used.

1.1 Scope of the curriculum

1.1.1 A baseline curriculum

The initial focus of the National Training Platform for Research Data Professionals is ‘on the development of a baseline curriculum and delivery of training for data professionals.’³ The current document clarifies the scope and purpose of the curriculum. It outlines the target audience and presents a detailed competency framework. Also, an outline is provided of a national training programme and associated learning paths for data professionals in the Netherlands. This is a baseline curriculum: it lays the foundation for subsequent work in the project, in particular to identify gaps and expand the current training provision. A final version will be published at the end of the project, with the intention to become the national curriculum for data stewards in the Netherlands.

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- 1 Data Archiving and Networked Services, SURFsara (Netherlands), Health-RI, & 4TU.ResearchData. (2025). National training and community platform for research data professionals (Versie 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17952713>
 - 2 Open Science NL (2023). Open Science NL Work programme 2024-2025. Open Science NL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074873>
 - 3 Open Science NL (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074873>. p.8.

1.1.2 Data professional versus data steward

In its work programme, Open Science NL refers to a platform for ‘data professionals’ and RDNL has always used the term ‘data professional’ for their target audience. The term ‘data professional’ is often used to indicate a broad range of professions in data driven research, such as data engineers, data analysts, data scientists, etc.⁴ For our curriculum, we therefore prefer a more precise term, which is now widely used in the Netherlands, and that more clearly refers to the specific tasks that lead to FAIR and open data: data steward. Research organisations in the Netherlands have official job profiles for ‘data steward’ or use it to refer to the role. Therefore, we use the term data steward in the rest of this document.

Although many competencies and topics that are relevant for data stewards can also be relevant for researchers, the focus of the project is on training specifically targeted at data stewards. This notion is defined in Chapter 2.

1.1.3 Training versus education

The national curriculum focuses on life-long learning (LLL), ‘learning to do’ that can be applied immediately on the job. It does not offer a formal education such as a bachelor’s or master’s degree for data stewards. Therefore, we use the term training(s) instead of education.

A glossary of terms and abbreviations can be found in [Appendix C](#).

1.2 Who is the curriculum intended for?

The curriculum is primarily relevant for:

- ▶ Data stewards in Dutch Research Performing Organisations: the curriculum aims to help data stewards professionalise and grow in their careers, particularly but not limited to the Dutch context. It will not only focus on novice data stewards, but also on experienced data stewards who seek more in-depth knowledge or specialisation in specific areas.
- ▶ Employers of data stewards: the curriculum gives employers of data stewards a way to make explicit what competencies they expect from a data steward and will help them develop their workforce through appropriate training opportunities.
- ▶ Training providers of data stewardship-related training: the curriculum can help training providers,

4 SSA Group (2021). Data professionals: An overview of specialisations and responsibilities. <https://www.ssa.group/blog/data-professionals-an-overview/>. Accessed 2025-12-08.

including RDNL, to understand and improve the relevance of their training content for the data steward profession and potentially include their training in the national training programme.

1.3 Elements of the curriculum

Organising training for professionals in an evolving field such as data stewardship requires flexibility to adapt to changing requirements. It is the intention of the curriculum to lay the foundation on which to build a flexible and future-proof national training programme. The national curriculum will consist of the following components:

1. A description of the data steward

A clear description of the role, tasks and the position of the data steward within the organisation (Chapter 2).

2. A competency framework

A framework that specifies what competencies data stewards can develop and that defines the boundaries of the national training programme (Chapter 3).

3. A training programme and learning paths

A national training programme, with trainings offered by RDNL and other training providers. Each training can form a building block in a learning path (Chapter 4).

4. Assessment and badging policy

A policy document on assessment and badging criteria to recognise the competencies gained by learners in different parts of the training programme, preferably by digital badging. This document will be published as a separate deliverable in Q1 2026.

5. Partnerships with other training providers

RDNL will set up collaborations with other training providers to create a relevant national training programme for data professionals which is in line with the RDNL competency framework (more information in Chapter 5).

2. The data steward

2.1 Research data stewardship in the Netherlands

Although the term data steward has been used in industry for decades, it only recently made its entry as a job title in higher education, alongside designations such as data librarian, data manager and data professional.⁵ The Netherlands was a frontrunner in describing data stewards' tasks and responsibilities in several reports published since 2019.⁶ The reports prompted the development of job profiles for data stewards at universities of applied sciences⁷, university medical centres⁸ and universities, with the latter being a formal job profile in the national classification system (UFO) since 2021.⁹ Thanks to investments by research organisations and to funding provided by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) in the context of the local Digital Competence Centres¹⁰, data stewardship capacity has grown significantly over the past years in the Netherlands. In 2024, data steward was even the fastest growing profession, according to LinkedIn.¹¹

2.2 What is a data steward?

Data stewardship is defined as a “course of action taken by a person or group to manage and supervise organisational data assets with responsibility and commitment. Good stewardship involves adequate

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- 5 Hansen, K. K., White, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Rauste, P., & van Leersum, N. (2025). Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006763>
 - 6 LCRDM report: Verheul, I., Imming, M., Ringerma, J., Mordant, A., Ploeg, J.-L. van der., & Pronk, M. (2019). Data Stewardship on the map: A study of tasks and roles in Dutch research institutes. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2669149>
ZonMw report: Scholtens, S., Jetten, M., Böhmer, J., Staiger, C., Slouwerhof, I., Van der Geest, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2022). Final report: Towards FAIR data steward as profession for the lifesciences. Report of a ZonMw funded collaborative approach built on existing expertise (Versie 4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3471707>
NPOS-F report: Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>
 - 7 DCC-PO (July 2023). Handreiking Organisatie Datastewardship op Hogescholen. <https://dcc-po.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/HANDRE3.pdf>
 - 8 See the example for RadboudUMC in Jetten et al. (2021), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>, p.122-130.
 - 9 The job profile for data stewards as part of the UFO classification system is not (yet) public, <https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/en/job-classification-system-ufo>
 - 10 Dutch Research Council (n.d.). Digital Competence Centres. <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/implementation-plan-investments-digital-research-infrastructure>. Accessed 2025-08-26.
 - 11 DANS-KNAW (23 February 2024). Data Steward, the fastest growing job. <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/news/data-steward-the-fastest-growing-job/>. Accessed 2025-08-26.

care, making use of the FAIR principles, and holding ownership and regulation to provide high-quality data (including metadata), combining trust and ethical practice.”¹²

Within this curriculum, we refer to data stewards as the staff members who perform data stewardship tasks within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). These can be full-time ‘data stewards’ but also researchers or other staff members who have been assigned data stewardship responsibilities.

2.3 Data stewards’ tasks

The starting point for the national curriculum is the formal job profile for data stewards in use at Dutch Universities (UFO).¹³ The UFO job profile describes five main activities for data stewards:

1. Policy development
2. (Continuous) development of RDM services and products
3. Advice and information
4. Knowledge, quality and process improvement
5. Coordination of work

Within the UFO profile, a data steward can be classified as one of four function levels (Data Steward 4 through 1), with increasing responsibilities and scope of the work per function level and across all five activities. For example, for the activity ‘policy development’, Data Steward 1 should take initiative and develop such policies, whereas someone in the position of Data Steward 4 only needs to contribute to RDM policy proposals.

Despite this unified profile, in daily practice, being a data steward encompasses a large variety of roles and responsibilities, depending on, for example:

- ▶ the type of organisation, e.g., university, university medical centre, university of applied sciences, another research institute;
- ▶ the position in the organisation, e.g., central, embedded in a research department or group;
- ▶ the expertise in the data steward team, e.g. one multitasker, versus a large team with different expertise and specialisations;
- ▶ the maturity of the support structure;
- ▶ the scientific discipline.

12 CODATA Research Data Management Terminology, <https://terms.codata.org/rdmt/data-stewardship>

13 In the assignment received by Open Science NL, RDNL was requested to align the curriculum to the UFO profile. UFO is the Dutch University Job Classification System. Individual University Medical Centres (UMCs) and Universities of Applied Sciences (UoAS) do have official job profiles, but these are not yet formalised within national job classification systems. Therefore, we do not mention them here, but we have taken their specific characteristics into account where possible.

For example, the LCRDM report describes three task area that data stewards can focus on: Policy, strategy and coordination; Generic and advice; and Embedded and operational.¹⁴ The NPOS-F report distinguishes policy-, research- and infrastructure-oriented data stewards, with a larger range of tasks and required competencies.¹⁵ Finally, the Skills4EOSC Minimal Viable Skillset for data stewards distinguishes between two types of data steward, each with its own tasks and required competencies: ‘coordinating’ vs. ‘embedded’.¹⁶

2.4 A data steward curriculum

We can conclude that, as described by the Turing Way Community, “Data Steward is an umbrella term for numerous support roles”.¹⁷ This means that, although the UFO profile and other sources mentioned here can give us a starting point, there is no uniform data steward with a fixed set of tasks, as depicted fittingly in Figure 1. Instead, data stewards have diverse backgrounds and specialisations, and therefore diverse responsibilities and training needs.

This implies that the national curriculum should cater to a wide variety of knowledge and skills in many different areas, sometimes basic, sometimes in-depth. The RDNL competency framework below seeks to ensure that this variety is captured. This will allow to accommodate the individual training needs of all those active in research data stewardship in the Netherlands.

Figure 1: A superhero-representation for the core responsibilities of a Data Steward. This image is an adaption of the image created by Scriberia for The Turing Way community. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4323154> (CC-BY).

14 Verheul et al. (2019). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2669149>

15 Jetten et al. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>

16 Hansen et al. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006763>

17 The Turing Way Community (2025). The Turing Way: A handbook for reproducible, ethical and collaborative research.

Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3233853>,

URL: <https://book.the-turing-way.org/collaboration/research-infrastructure-roles/data-steward/>. Accessed 2025-12-03.

3. RDNL competency framework for data stewards

3.1 Why a competency framework?

As described in the previous section, the national curriculum should cater to a wide variety of data stewardship activities and competencies. A competency framework provides a common ground that allows all providers of training to data stewards in the Netherlands to:

- ▶ Scope what is considered to fall within or outside the national curriculum;
- ▶ Map the competencies taught in existing trainings and discover for which competencies new trainings need to be developed;
- ▶ Build a coherent training programme that covers the many directions into which data stewards can specialise and create learning paths catering to these specialisations.

3.2 RDNL competency framework

Many competency frameworks already exist for data stewards and other data-related professions. The RDNL competency framework has been compiled by combining existing frameworks, adjusting them to allow easier use for training purposes and adding input received from data stewards and other stakeholders. We refer to it as the RDNL competency framework to distinguish it from these other frameworks – ideally it becomes the Dutch Data Steward competency framework. For a full description of the sources used for the framework, please refer to [Appendix B](#).

3.3 Competency areas

The RDNL competency framework is organised into seven competency areas relevant for data stewards in Research Performing Organisations in the Netherlands. Every competency area represents a broad aspect of data stewardship. We expect that all data stewards need a basic understanding of all areas, but some competencies within these areas will lend themselves better for further specialisation. Importantly, the competency framework does not explicitly cover discipline-specific training needs, whereas these can be important for a subset of data stewards.

The seven competency areas, the order not necessarily reflecting the importance:

- 1. RDM, FAIR principles & open science** covers competencies required for providing tailored advice, curating datasets, and providing hands-on data management in line with good research

data management (RDM) practices and the FAIR and open science principles. It also includes the development and monitoring of RDM services. We expect that most, if not all, data stewards need to be able to demonstrate some competency in this area.

2. **Research Software Management** covers competencies required for providing tailored advice about research software management and computational reproducibility and applying these topics hands-on. As research software engineer (RSE) is a distinct position, we expect that this area is relevant for a subset of data stewards, for example, for those in small organisations without access to RSEs or for those wishing to specialise in this direction.
3. **Data infrastructure** covers the availability of adequate digital infrastructure for RDM, such as for data storage, transfer, analysis and publication. It includes competencies required for providing tailored advice about infrastructure and tools, and contributing to the infrastructure and tools available for researchers. We expect most data stewards to require some competencies in this area, in order to properly advise researchers, but this area may also function as further specialisation for data stewards with responsibilities for specific infrastructure.
4. **Policy and governance** covers competencies required for the development, implementation and monitoring of RDM policy and strategy. We expect this area to be relevant as a further specialisation or suitable for data stewards who have an active role in RDM policy.
5. **Legal and ethical responsibilities** covers competencies required to advise about compliance with relevant scientific, legal, and ethical standards. We expect that this area is relevant for most, if not all, data stewards, but it may depend on the specific discipline or role which laws, regulations or standards are most relevant. Specialisation in this area is also a possibility, such as in data protection, ethics or intellectual property.
6. **Training and awareness raising** covers competencies to assess and ascertain an adequate level of knowledge and skills on RDM within the organisation. We expect that this area is most relevant for data stewards who provide training or write guidance for researchers.
7. **Transversal skills**, also known as ‘soft’ or ‘non-cognitive skills’, cover competencies that can be used in a wide variety of settings. Many data stewards we spoke to went as far as to indicate that transversal skills are the most important competency category, one that distinguishes their work from that of researchers. The RDNL competency framework focusses primarily on those transversal skills that we identified as relating most explicitly to the duties of a data steward, such as networking, effectively communicating, and managing RDM projects.

3.4 Structure of the competency framework

In the RDNL competency framework, every competency area consists of one or more competencies relevant to data stewardship. Each competency is underpinned by supporting knowledge (K) and skills (S) that could be acquired a.o. through training.¹⁸ For example:

- ▶ The competency to “curate and evaluate datasets for long-term preservation” (competency 1B) requires the ability to apply the FAIR data principles.
- ▶ To “ensure a sufficient level of awareness, knowledge and skills among researchers and research support staff” (competency 6B), a data steward should be able to design RDM-related training and provide training in an engaging manner.

In addition to competencies and supporting knowledge and skills, each area includes Topics relevant to the competency area, with links to definitions of these topics. Topics are more granular items that may also be targeted in training and may involve specific technologies (e.g., Linked Open Data, 3-point FAIRification framework, software version control) or subject-matter knowledge (e.g., knowledge of relevant legislation, costs of RDM, CARE principles) needed to demonstrate a competency.

3.5 Using the RDNL competency framework

In practice, we foresee that trainings likely cover a combination of supporting knowledge and skills, and topics. The competency framework is not prescriptive, however, and RDNL does not intend to develop training for every single knowledge item, skill or topic. Rather, it provides a structured overview to map existing trainings and find gaps where new trainings are most needed. As such, the competency framework helps guide the development of trainings and build a national training programme corresponding to the needs of data stewards in their everyday jobs.

The full competency framework can be found in [Appendix A](#). The sources used for the framework are described in [Appendix B](#).

18 The terms “Supporting knowledge and skills” come from Green, D., & Levy, C. (2021). EcampusOntario Competency Toolkit. <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/competencytoolkit/>. Competency models often refer to Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes. The RDNL competency framework focusses on knowledge and skills only, as these are typically addressed in training.

4. Training programme and learning paths

The national training programme is a collection of training courses for data professionals that address the competency areas from the RDNL competency framework. Within the training programme, each training forms a ‘building block’, each with its own planning, prerequisites, content, learning objectives and assessment method. These building blocks can then be used to create learning paths. The relationship between the competency framework, training programme, individual trainings and learning paths is visualised in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Relation between the RDNL competency framework with seven competency areas and the training programme.

This programme builds on the competency framework and will be developed incrementally in the coming period.

Each training has its own planning, prerequisites, learning objectives, etc. and can be a building block in a learning path.

4.1 Training blocks

Training offers may change over time, for example because new trainings are developed, new collaborations are created, or trainings are discontinued. As mentioned in the Open Science NL work programme 2024-2025, where needed, more training will be developed to “cater for data professionals at different career stages and with different types of expertise (e.g., working with software, working with personal research data, technical expertise and databases)”.¹⁹ Therefore, the training programme will necessarily be a dynamic collection of trainings. Currently, the existing and planned building blocks of the training programme are:

- ▶ RDNL’s Essentials 4 Data Support;²⁰

¹⁹ Open Science NL. (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074873>, p.8.

- ▶ RDNL’s GDPR 4 Data Support;²¹
- ▶ RDNL’s Train-the-trainer course (to be developed in 2026).

These trainings will be complemented by relevant trainings provided by individual RDNL partners and by external training providers. For example, in addition to RDNL partner trainings (e.g., Health-RI’s FAIR Data Stewards basics course²²), we have started discussions with:

- ▶ eScience Center about their Research Software Support training;²³
- ▶ LCRDM about workshops from the DCC Spring Training Days;²⁴
- ▶ DCC-PO for data steward trainings in Universities of Applied Sciences.²⁵

4.2 Building learning paths

Designing a training programme for data stewards requires viewing professional growth as a continuous learning path. A learning path can be defined as a ‘pathway that guides learners through a set of learning courses or materials to be undertaken progressively to acquire the desired knowledge and skills on a subject of interest’.²⁶ Along such a path, data stewards can build expertise depending on their individual needs. Also, organisations can propose recommended or even mandatory learning paths for their data stewards.

Unlike the commonly used progression model (beginner, intermediate, advanced), there are no standard definitions for these levels in the context of research data stewardship in the Netherlands:

- ▶ The UFO profile used by universities defines four levels, but these are primarily based on scope of work and responsibilities, not on required knowledge or skills.
- ▶ Completing trainings does not necessarily guarantee a progression between UFO levels (e.g., from Data Steward 3 to Data Steward 2).
- ▶ Each data steward has different training needs and one skill or topic should not necessarily be considered more ‘advanced’ than the other. For example, a data steward could have in-depth knowledge about handling

20 A full course description of Essentials 4 Data Support can be found on:

<https://researchdata.nl/en/essentials-4-data-support/>

21 A full course description of GDPR 4 Data Support can be found on: <https://researchdata.nl/en/gdpr-4-data-support/>

22 A full course description of the FAIR data stewards basics course can be found on:

<https://www.healthdata.nl/en/services/fair-data-stewards-basics-course>. Accessed 2025-12-16.

23 The materials for this course can be found on: <https://esciencecenter-digital-skills.github.io/research-software-support/>.

24 Materials from the 2025 round of workshops can be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dccspring2025/>.

25 For their current offer, please see the DCC-PO website: <https://dcc-po.nl/>

26 Definition by the Elixir Learning Paths Focus Group, <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/learning-paths>. Accessed 2025-12-16.

personal data but have limited knowledge about research software management or policy making.

Therefore, RDNL approaches expertise development as an ongoing process, rather than as discrete levels. Learning paths should be built based on a training's content-based prerequisite knowledge (e.g., "requires a basic understanding of the FAIR principles") and learning objectives (e.g., using the Bloom's taxonomy²⁷), with each training building on the other. This approach enables data stewards and their employers to interpret how each training fits their individual professional journey.

4.3 Example learning paths

RDNL will prepare a selection of pre-made learning paths, the contents of which depend on needs of data stewards and the availability of training. These learning paths will enable data stewards to acquire more general knowledge to progress in their career, specialise further into a specific competency area, or specialise into a scientific discipline. In the following examples, visualised in Figure 3 below, we only refer to currently existing or planned trainings:

Specialisation in the area of legal and ethical responsibilities, relevant for data stewards supporting research with personal data:

- ▶ Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ GDPR 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ Advanced Anonymization and Pseudonymization (DCC Spring Training Days).

Specialisation in the area of Research software management, relevant for data stewards supporting researchers writing research software:

- ▶ Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ Research Software Support training (eScience Center).

Specialisation in the area of Training and awareness raising, relevant for data stewards who frequently provide RDM-related training:

- ▶ Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ Train-the-trainer course (RDNL);
- ▶ Practical pedagogical techniques for hands-on workshops (DCC Spring Training Days).

Specialisation in the life sciences discipline, relevant for data stewards in university medical centres:

- ▶ Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ FAIR Data Stewards basic course for Life Sciences & Health (Health-RI)

27 Bloom, B. S.; Engelhart, M. D.; Furst, E. J.; Hill, W. H.; Krathwohl, D. R. (1956). Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Vol. Handbook I: Cognitive domain. New York: David McKay Company.

Specialisation into a specific organisational context. In this case, relevant for data stewards at Universities of Applied Sciences:

- ▶ Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL);
- ▶ Training FAIR data management (DCC-PO);²⁸
- ▶ Zoeken, vinden en beoordelen van onderzoeksdata (DCC Spring Training Days by DCC-PO);
- ▶ Training Publiceren en Archiveren (DCC-PO).

Figure 3: Example of the training programme as a collection of building blocks. Each block represents a training, course or set of modules that fits the RDNL competency framework. Arrows indicate learning paths from left to right.

²⁸ <https://dcc-po.nl/agenda/training-fair-data-management/>. Accessed 2025-11-11.

5. Next steps

This document is a first step towards a national curriculum for data stewards in the Dutch research landscape. For RDNL, it is explicitly a starting point for further collaboration with training providers, data stewards, the organisations where they are employed, service providers, and other relevant stakeholders. Activities to come in the coming three years will further shape the curriculum and will include:

1. **Mapping:** The competency framework will be used to map existing trainings suitable for data stewards, including trainings from other training providers, and to identify gaps where new training needs to be developed. This mapping will be done in collaboration with training providers and is planned for Q1 2026.
2. **Badging:** A badging policy will be written to determine a badging scheme and how badges will be used in the context of the national training programme. This policy is expected in Q1 2026.
3. **Expanding the training programme:** RDNL will collaborate with training providers to:
 - a. complement the training programme with existing trainings relevant for data stewards;
 - b. collaboratively develop new training for data stewards, where needed; and
 - c. define rules of participation that specify when trainings may be included in the training programme and what the roles and responsibilities of RDNL and the training providers are, respectively.To this end, we will pilot a collaboration process with selected partners prior to having an open call for participation by a wider range of training providers.
4. **Feedback loop:** RDNL plans to actively gather input from, and collaborate with, data stewards, training providers, and other relevant stakeholders to ensure endorsement and uptake of the national training programme. This will be a continuous process throughout the coming three years and includes validation of the current document.

With these steps, RDNL hopes to shape a curriculum that fits the needs of data stewards in Dutch Research Performing Organisations.

List of resources

B

Bloom, B. S.; Engelhart, M. D.; Furst, E. J.; Hill, W. H.; Krathwohl, D. R. (1956). Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Vol. Handbook I: Cognitive domain. New York: David McKay Company.

C

Cedefop, Terminology of European education and training policy,
<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/vet-glossary/glossary>

CODATA Research Data Management Terminology,
<https://terms.codata.org/rdmt/data-stewardship>

D

DANS-KNAW (23 February 2024). Data Steward, the fastest growing job.
<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/news/data-steward-the-fastest-growing-job/>

DCC-PO (July 2023). Handreiking Organisatie Datastewardship op Hogescholen.
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Appendix A: RDNL competency framework

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
1. RDM, FAIR principles & open science	<p>1A. Provide tailored advice about RDM solutions and FAIR data across the research data lifecycle, in line with relevant policies and requirements</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Data definitions and data responsibilities in research [K] The research process and the research data lifecycle [K] The FAIR data principles [K] Open science principles and practices [K] Importance and benefits of RDM, FAIR data and open science [K] Role of research data in scholarly communication [K] Requirements, templates and tools for data management planning [K] The institute's organisational structure and processes [S] Assist researchers with and review Data Management Plans [S] Assist researchers with (systematic) discovery and reuse of existing datasets 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Research data Scientific disciplines Research methodologies Research data lifecycle Roles and responsibilities in RDM Open science Reproducibility and replicability Scholarly communication Costs for RDM Data management planning FAIR data principles Data discovery Data reuse Data collection Data documentation Data organisation File naming (conventions) Data versioning Data formats and types Data back-up Data selection
	<p>1B. Curate and evaluate datasets for long-term preservation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Apply the FAIR principles [S] Share data effectively [S] Evaluate and improve the FAIRness of datasets [S] Formulate and apply data preservation strategies 	
	<p>1C. Deliver / provide hands-on data management</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Apply and advise researchers on designing efficient and secure data (integration) workflows 	

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
1. RDM, FAIR principles & open science	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. [S] Implement data quality, validation, and cleaning mechanisms into the research process 3. [S] Create metadata and documentation using appropriate schemas and standards 4. [S] Support the development, mapping, and implementation of metadata standards 5. [S] Develop and implement relevant data models 6. [S] Work with data stored in databases (e.g. SQL, noSQL) and advise researchers on their application 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 22. Data destruction 23. Data preservation and archiving 24. Data publication 25. Data curation 26. Data visualisation 27. Data provenance 28. Metadata (standard) 29. Controlled vocabulary, ontology, taxonomy, thesaurus 30. Linked Open Data and SPARQL 31. FAIR metrics 32. 3-point FAIRification Framework (FAIR data point, FAIR Implementation Profile) 33. Persistent identifier 34. Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) 35. Spreadsheet tools 36. Data modelling 37. Data integration 38. Data integrity, validation & quality 39. Data cleaning & wrangling 40. Database management 41. Master data management 42. Business intelligence 43. RDM service models
	<p>1D. Develop and monitor RDM support and services</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [K] Relevant support and services available for RDM, both internally as well as externally 2. [S] Assess and analyse needs regarding support on RDM and define new requirements 3. [S] Initiate or supervise the set-up and update of suitable support facilities or services 4. [S] Communicate about and stimulate the use of available services 5. [S] Monitor and evaluate the uptake and effectiveness of RDM services 	

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
2. Research Software Management (RSM)	<p>2A. Provide tailored advice about Research Software Management</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Different levels of research software (e.g. scripts, code, independent software) [S] Write and advise on creating a Software Management Plan [S] Advise on storing, documenting, publishing, licensing, and citing research software [S] Assist researchers with (systematic) discovery and reuse of existing research software 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Research software Software management planning Software version control (e.g., git and GitHub) Software documentation Software packaging (R, Python, etc.) Software citation FAIR software Reproducibility Coding conventions Literate programming Scientific workflows and data pipelines Computer programming Virtual environments and Containerisation Continuous integration Use of generative Artificial Intelligence in writing research software
	<p>2B. Provide tailored advice on reproducibility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] The FAIR principles for research software and the difference between FAIR, Open source, and good quality research software [K] How to embed research software in scientific workflows [S] Advise on good coding practices and tools to enhance reproducibility of research results [S] Evaluate and improve reproducibility of research projects that use research software 	
	<p>2C. Hands-on research software management and reproducibility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Support researchers in publishing their research software [S] Use and advise on version control systems [S] Write and assess software documentation [S] Understand, write, and evaluate basic programming code to automate (parts of) relevant stages of the research data lifecycle 	

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
3. Data infrastructure	<p>3A. Provide tailored advice to researchers about data infrastructure and tools in the research data lifecycle</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Relevant facilities, data infrastructure, tools and emerging standards relevant to RDM (e.g. data collection tools, statistical programmes, etc.) [K] RDM issues related to data infrastructure and tools in the data lifecycle [S] Use data infrastructure and tools relevant to RDM [S] Provide access, guidance and training on proper use of data infrastructure and tools relevant to RDM 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Certified) Data Repositories Repository quality standards (e.g. CoreTrustSeal, ISAD(G), OAIS reference model) TRUST principles for digital repositories Tool criticism Data collection tools Data management services/tools Data storage (media) Data transfer tools Data analysis software/tools Cloud computing and High-performance computing Data security and Data classification Available RDM infrastructure and organisations European Open Science Cloud solutions
	<p>3B. Assess and analyse needs regarding data infrastructure and tools for RDM for researchers and relevant stakeholders and translate these needs to requirements and advice</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Monitor and evaluate effectiveness and use(ability) of data infrastructure [S] Analyse data infrastructure and tool needs [S] Translate needs to advice for local, national or international implementation [S] Facilitate proper alignment of data infrastructure to relevant external data infrastructure and tools [S] Facilitate proper alignment between researcher needs and IT-related departments within the organisation 	
4. Policy and Governance	<p>4A. Policy Development (stakeholders, (inter)national developments)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Importance of institutional policies such as data and software policy [K] Elements of an RDM policy [K] Policy development cycle and tools [K] Interplay between data, software, AI policy and ethical/legal frameworks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> European, national and institutional policies on RDM, RSM and open science Funder RDM, RSM and open science requirements

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
4. Policy and Governance	5. [K] Relevant internal and external stakeholders and their requirements and needs	3. Journal policies related to RDM
	6. [S] Ensure alignment between institutional, national and international RDM-related policies and practices	4. Policy development
	7. [S] Contribute actively to national and international RDM policy development	5. Policy implementation
	4B. Policy implementation (communication, stakeholder engagement, translation into actionable strategies)	6. Policy monitoring
	1. [S] Communicate about RDM policies, explain implications and create awareness	7. Translating policy to organisational strategy
	2. [S] Turn national and international developments into RDM policy and implementation within the institute]	8. Responsible metrics (bibliometrics , altmetrics)
	3. [S] Translate institutional policies into actionable data management strategies	9. Digital sovereignty
	4C. Monitoring and evaluation of policy compliance and impact	10. Data governance
	1. [S] Assess and monitor compliance to the FAIR data principles and the principles of open science	11. Data ownership
	2. [S] Evaluate and monitor effectiveness of and compliance to policy	12. Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for RDM
	4D. Data governance and sovereignty	
	1. [S] Advise relevant parties on opportunities for collaboration with internal and external organisations	
2. [S] Advise management on data governance and data sovereignty issues, infrastructure and procedures to put in place		
3. [S] Advise on conditions for sharing and collaborating on data with parties outside the own institution / Netherlands / EU		

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
5. Legal and ethical responsibilities	<p>5A. Advise on applicable legislation, regulations and codes of conduct</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Legislation, ethics and codes of conduct with regards to research data [K] Responsible use of AI and relevant AI legislation, policies and guidelines [S] Translate legislation, regulations and codes of conducts to practical implications and guidelines [S] Identify and manage ethical and legal risks in a research context and know when to refer to ethical/legal experts [S] Facilitate proper alignment between researcher needs and legal and ethical departments within the organisation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Privacy and data protection (GDPR, UAVG) Sensitive data/Confidentiality Intellectual property rights <ol style="list-style-type: none"> copyright patents trademarks Research in consortia Data and software licenses License compatibility Information security Knowledge security European data legislation <ol style="list-style-type: none"> AI Act Data Governance Act Data Act European Health Data Space (Cyber)security legislation, e.g. NIS2 Directive Trade Secret Protection Act Research ethics and integrity CARE principles Diversity, equity & inclusion

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
6. Training and awareness raising	<p>6A. Assess RDM knowledge and skills and identify gaps among researchers and relevant stakeholders</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Required level of knowledge for researchers and relevant stakeholders [K] Available RDM training opportunities and possibilities 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Needs assessment Instructional design <ol style="list-style-type: none"> FAIR-by-Design methodology Carpentries methodology Training andragogy
	<p>6B. Ensure a sufficient level of awareness, knowledge and skills among researchers and research support staff</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Translate RDM policies and DMPs to practical implications and guidelines that researchers can understand [S] (Coordinate the) design (of) RDM-related training and tailor it to the target audience [S] Plan, organise and execute training and awareness-related events [S] Find, reuse and FAIRify training materials [S] Provide training in an engaging, inclusive and accessible manner [S] Advocate for integration of training and awareness activities in curricula, onboarding, or staff development programmes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Didactic methods Presentation skills Written communication skills Open Educational Resources Diagnostic, formative and summative assessment Course evaluation Student satisfaction
	<p>6C. Evaluate the effectiveness and impact of training and awareness activities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [S] Assess learning outcomes and student satisfaction for provided training and awareness activities [S] Monitor and evaluate the impact and effectiveness of awareness activities 	
7. Transversal Skills	<p>7A. Professional skills</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> [K] Knowledge about the data steward's tasks and responsibilities [S] Lead or mentor colleagues [S] Work effectively in a(n interdisciplinary) team 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Networking skills Community management Existing RDM networks/ communities Consultancy

Competency area	Competencies & supporting Knowledge [K] and Skills [S]	Topics
	<p>4. [S] Navigate the complex structures, rules, power dynamics, and interpersonal relationships within research organisations</p>	<p>5. Advocacy</p> <p>6. Conflict resolution</p> <p>7. Negotiating</p> <p>8. Active listening</p>
	<p>7B. Build and maintain networks</p> <p>1. [K] Where to find decision makers, RDM experts, researchers, and other stakeholders, including relevant (RDM) networks</p> <p>2. [S] Identify and participate in local, national and international RDM networks</p> <p>3. [K] The principles of community building and management</p> <p>4. [S] Establish and maintain an active network in the field of RDM</p> <p>5. [S] Connect data support staff in- and outside the institute (liaising)</p>	<p>9. Stakeholder analysis</p> <p>10. Stakeholder engagement</p> <p>11. Organisational development</p> <p>12. Project management (methodologies)</p> <p>13. Change management</p> <p>14. Binding Leadership</p>
	<p>7C. Advise and communicate effectively with stakeholders across disciplines and roles</p> <p>1. [S] Advocate for the importance of open science, research data management and data support with management and researchers</p> <p>2. [S] Communicate effectively with a diverse range of stakeholders</p> <p>3. [S] Think outside the box, generate new ideas, and find novel solutions to problems or opportunities</p>	<p>15. Facilitation</p> <p>16. Teamwork</p>
	<p>7D. Manage RDM-related projects effectively</p> <p>1. [S] Facilitate inclusive and purpose-driven meetings or discussions</p> <p>2. [S] Effectively set-up and manage RDM-related projects (planning, coordination, monitoring, reporting)</p> <p>3. [S] Accomplish sustainable change through strategies and personal influence</p> <p>4. [S] Assess information, weigh options, consider potential outcomes, and choose the best course of action in a given situation</p>	

Appendix B: Sources of the RDNL competency framework

The RDNL competency framework is largely based on:

- ▶ Activities in the formal university profile for data stewards (UFO).
- ▶ The ‘NPOS-F report’³¹ and accompanying competency framework³². This framework provided the basis for the UFO job profile and provides detailed Activities, Knowledge and Skills relevant for the RDNL competency framework.
- ▶ The Skills4EOSC Curriculum for entry-level data stewards³³. This curriculum is internationally recognised, builds on earlier frameworks and was piloted in practice. It also builds on the Skills4EOSC Minimum Viable Skills Profile for Data Stewards.³⁴

Additionally, the following sources were used to complement the above listed sources:

- ▶ The German NFDI4Health’s learning matrix for Research Data Management.³⁵
- ▶ The FAIRsFAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (Data Stewardship Professional Competence Framework)³⁶ was used to complement Topics.
- ▶ The EDISON Data Science Competence Framework³⁷ was used for complementary competencies and phrasings.

31 Jetten et al. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504>

32 The competency framework was developed in the ZonMW report (Scholtens et al, 2022), was further expanded within the NPOS-F project (Jetten et al., 2021) and can be consulted via: <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/datasteward/1.0>

33 van Leersum, N., Sharma, S., Winandi, A., Martinez Lavanchy, P. M., Aguilar Gómez, F., Alamettälä, T., Antoine, D., Bernier, M., Colcelli, V., Derksen, B., Drajewski, K., Green, D., Hadrossek, C., Janik, J., Hansen, K. K., Leister, C., Møldrup-Dalum, P., Musidlowska, M., Peters, E., ... Wildgaard, L. (2025, July 9). Data Steward Training Curriculum. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15848853>. URL: <https://skills4eosc-dscurriculum.github.io/DataSteward-Training-Curriculum/latest/>

34 Hansen et al. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006763>

35 Petersen, B., Altemeier, F., BoBe, S., Dalby, M., Düvel, N., Engelhardt, C., Fichtner, M., Hastik, C., Haugwitz, J.-M., Jacob, J., Koch, K., Kuntz, A., Manske, A., Mühlichen, A., Murcia Serra, J., Ortmeier, J., Richter, M., Schranzhofer, H., Slowig, B., ... Zollitsch, L. (2025). Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) (Version 3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15025246>

36 Demchenko, Y., Stoy, L., Engelhardt, C., & Gaillard, V. (2021). D7.3 FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (Data Stewardship Professional Competence Framework) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361917>. URL: https://fairsfair.gitbook.io/fair-teaching-handbook/0fairskillscompetences/2_1method/2_2competenceprofiles

37 Demchenko, Y., Belloum, A., & Wiktorski, T. (2017). EDISON Data Science Framework: Part 1. Data Science Competence Framework (CF-DS) Release 2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1044346>

- ▶ The Competence Instrument for the Dutch Universities, 4th revised edition³⁸ was used to complement the transversal skills.
- ▶ The Digital Research Competencies Framework (DIRECT)³⁹ was used to complement technical skills and transversal skills.
- ▶ Several data steward vacancies advertised in 2024-2025 were scanned to complement the framework.

To help structure and phrase the competencies, we additionally used the Competency framework of the Digital Preservation Coalition⁴⁰ and the ECampusOntario Competency Toolkit⁴¹.

38 Vereniging van Universiteiten - VSNU (2016). Competence Instrument for the Dutch Universities.

<https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/files/publications/Vernieuwd%20Competence%20Instrument%20Dutch%20Universities%202016-%20EN.pdf>. Accessed on 2025-11-11.

39 Digital Research Competencies Framework (DIRECT). <https://directframework.com/competencies/>. Accessed 2025-11-11.

40 McMeekin, S., & Currie, A. (2025). Digital Preservation Competency Framework 2nd Edition. Digital Preservation Coalition. https://doi.org/10.7207/dpccf25_02

41 Green, D., & Levy, C. (2021). EcampusOntario Competency Toolkit. <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/competencytoolkit/> (CC-BY-SA 4.0).

Appendix C: Glossary of terms

Item	Description	Source
Assessment of learning outcomes	Process of appraising knowledge, know-how, information, values, skills and competences – acquired in formal, non-formal or informal settings – against relevant standards (learning outcomes, validation).	https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/vet-glossary/glossary
Bloom's taxonomy	Bloom's taxonomy is a widely used framework for categorising educational goals in six levels: Remember, Understand, Apply, Analyse, Evaluate and Create.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bloom%27s_taxonomy
Competence	Proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and in professional and personal development. We use the term 'competency' here, since this is very broad and not necessarily related to training.	https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/about-esco/escopedia/escopedia/competence?id=121
Competency	The specific and measurable combination of knowledge, skills and attributes that result in the performance of an activity or task to a defined level of expectation or performance standard.	https://ecampusontario.press-books.pub/competencytoolkit/back-matter/glossary/
DCC-PO	Digital Competence Center voor Praktijkgericht Onderzoek (for practice-oriented research)	https://dcc-po.nl/
Digital badge	A digitally issued credential that contains structured information that is standardised for easier sharing and can be evaluated and authenticated via embedded links. This leads to trusted recognition for learners and makes their credentials more portable and meaningful.	https://ecampusontario.press-books.pub/competencytoolkit/back-matter/glossary/

Item	Description	Source
Education	Formal school curricula at universities, university medical centres, and universities of applied sciences. Typically, these are semester courses, with a strong theoretical basis.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320504 (p.23)
Knowledge	The outcome of the assimilation of information through learning. Knowledge is the body of facts, principles, theories and practices that is related to a field of work or study.	https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/about-esco/escopedia/escopedia/knowledge
KSA - Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude	The combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (learning categories) that are essential for performing job-specific tasks effectively. The RDNL competency framework focusses on knowledge [K] and skills [S].	RDNL
LCRDM	National Coordination Point RDM (Landelijke Coördinatiepunt RDM)	https://lcrdm.nl/
Learning activities	The things the learner engages in doing to achieve the learning objectives. Learning activities may be lessons, assignments, projects, etc. and may or may not be graded or assessed.	https://ecampusontario.press-books.pub/competencytoolkit/back-matter/glossary/
LLL	Life Long Learning, 'learning to do' that can be applied immediately on the job, rather than offering a formal education.	RDNL
Learning objectives	They state the intended goals for smaller pieces of learning, such as for a single lesson or course module. (e.g. Each lesson in a course will have specific learning objectives.) Objectives usually focus on knowledge acquisition or development of discrete skills; describe process rather than the intended result and are aligned with learning outcomes.	https://ecampusontario.press-books.pub/competencytoolkit/back-matter/glossary/

Item	Description	Source
Learning outcomes	Broad statements of what someone will be able to do on completion of the learning intervention, usually at the end of a “course” or “program”. The learning outcome expresses the integrated learning by a student and explains what the learner will achieve.	https://ecampusontario.press-books.pub/competencytoolkit/back-matter/glossary/
Learning path	A pathway that guides learners through a set of learning courses or materials to be undertaken progressively to acquire the desired knowledge and skills on a subject of interest.	https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/learning-paths
NPOS	Nationaal Plan Open Science	https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:9e9fa82e-06c1-4d0d-9e20-5620259a6c65
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations	
Skill	The ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems. Skills can be “cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) or practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments).	https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/about-esco/escopedia/escopedia/skill?id=113
Teaching	A form of instruction, which can happen both in-person and online, in courses, workshops, e-learnings, etc.	RDNL
Training	Acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies as a result of teaching. Training is often shorter than courses in an educational setting and is tailored to the use of tools and to the implementation of the learning outcomes in daily practice.	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q918385 . See also table 2.3 in https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713 (p.24).
Training Programme	A collection of training courses that address the competency areas for data professionals from the framework	

rdnl Research Data
Netherlands

Research Data Netherlands is a national coalition of
4TU.ResearchData, DANS, Health-RI and SURF.

